

To Compare the Postoperative Analgesia of Ropivacaine Along with Dexmedetomidine and Ropivacaine Along with Fentanyl on Intraperitoneal Instillation in Patients Undergoing Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy

Ayushi Soni¹, Ruchi Tandon², Kumbha Gopi³, Amisha S Keshav⁴

^{1,3&4}Senior Resident, Department of Anaesthesiology, Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal, M.P.

²Head of Department, Department of Emergency Medicine, Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal, M.P.

Received: 11-06-2024 / Revised: 25-06-2024 / Accepted: 13-07-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Amisha S Keshav

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background & Methods: The aim of the study is to compare the postoperative analgesia of ropivacaine with dexmedetomidine and ropivacaine with fentanyl on intraperitoneal instillation in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy. After explaining the procedure and obtaining written/informed consent, a total of 60 patients fulfilling the inclusion criteria, scheduled to undergo elective laparoscopic surgeries under general anaesthesia (GA), were included in the study.

Results: There is not significant deference in all the vitals (pulse rate, systolic bp, diastolic bp, MAP, SpO₂, Respiratory rate) before surgery. p-value in all vitals more than 0.05 which is not significant. In this study Mean NRS score was significantly higher in fentanyl group then dexmedetomidine group during follow-up.

Conclusion: Our study is that in patients whom posted for elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy intraperitoneal instillation of 0.25% ropivacaine along with dexmedetomidine 1mcg/kg provide more effective and prolong analgesia compared to intraperitoneal instillation of 0.25% of ropivacaine with fentanyl 1mcg/kg postoperatively up till 24 hours. It also decrease the dose of rescue analgesia require and provide improved quality of analgesia in first 24 hours postoperatively.

Keywords: ropivacaine, dexmedetomidine, laparoscopic & cholecystectomy.

Study Design: Prospective Observational Study.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Pain is an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with actual or potential tissue damage. Surgical pain results from tissue inflammation following tissue trauma (i.e. surgical incision, dissection, burns) or direct nerve injury (i.e. nerve transection, stretching, or compression). The patient senses pain through the nociceptive system consisting of peripheral afferents, the spinal cord, brainstem, thalamus and cortex. [1]

Other than intraoperative pain, postoperative pain has been a major source of fear and anxiety in hospitalized patients. Although pain is a self-limiting phenomenon but a pain free postoperative phase increases patient's co-operation and activity levels, leading to early recovery. [2] Pain relief is not simply a humanitarian consideration but also an important means for reduction of morbidity and mortality. [3]

The scope of an anaesthesiologist is not only limited to the pre-operative and intra-operative care of the patients but it extends to the post-operative phase till the next 48 hours. [4] The main concern in the postoperative phase remains optimizing

patient's comfort and safety along with maximizing the analgesia. [5] Surgical stress leads to release of substance-P, prostaglandins, histamine, interleukins, and cytokines from the inflamed tissue. Various analgesics (NSAID's, opioid etc.) act at different levels in brain and spinal cord to produce their effects on pain pathway and other organ systems. [6]

Cholecystectomy is the second most common operative procedure performed worldwide today. The technique developed a century ago by a German surgeon, Carl Johann August Langenbuch, received little recognition on inception, but has now become the gold standard for the definitive management of symptomatic cholelithiasis. The gold standard, conventional invasive procedure i.e. open cholecystectomy(OC) has largely been replaced by laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC), which was first performed in 1987 by a French Surgeon, Phillipe Mouret. Since then, laparoscopic cholecystectomy has become treatment of choice in treating gallbladder diseases substituting the conventional open method

of cholecystectomy. LC has improved surgical outcome in terms of lesser bleeding, minimal tissue trauma, reduce pain, shorter recovery time, morbidity and decreased hospital stay thereby, leading to overall reduced healthcare costs. Most worthy achievement from patient's point of view is not a pain free procedure, that's why many LC patients refrain from early recovery to normal activity and imperils the feasibility of LC. [7]

Despite of all the advantages, like any other surgery, laparoscopic cholecystectomy is also associated with stress response induced by surgery and anaesthesia. The pneumoperitoneum and the position of the patient required for laparoscopy lead to many pathophysiological changes that complicate anaesthetic management. Following laparoscopic cholecystectomy, the post-operative pain may vary in intensity from moderate to severe; from patient to patient depending upon the extent of tissue trauma and personal tolerance, as pain being a highly personal and subjective experience. The type of pain following cholecystectomy differs considerably from that seen after open cholecystectomy. Previous studies advocate the etiology of postoperative pain in patients who underwent LC is multifactorial. [8]

Material and Methods

Pre-anaesthetic check-up of the patient selected for study was carried out a day prior to the surgery and was recorded as per Performa. In each case, a detailed history and physical examination was carried out prior to general anaesthesia. A Prospective, observational, hospital based clinical study was

conducted in department of Anaesthesiology, Gandhi Medical College and associated Hamidia Hospital, Bhopal. After approval by institutional ethics committee and written informed consent of 60 patients aged 18-60 years was taken into study who were given either ropivacaine with dexmedetomidine or ropivacaine with fentanyl.

The quality of analgesia was assessed by using acute pain scale- the visual analogue scale (VAS) and numerical rating scale(NRS). Time to the first request of analgesia, the total dose of analgesia in first 24hr and adverse effects was noted.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients of all gender between 18-65 years of age.
- ASA physical status grade I/II patients.
- Patient who are willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Refusal of patient to participate in the study.
- Patients with significant systemic illness.
- History of allergy to drugs under study.
- Pregnant and lactating women.
- Morbid obesity (BMI>40 kg/m²).
- Patients with chronic pain syndrome and coagulation disorders.
- History of previous abdominal surgery.
- Patients in whom conversion to open cholecystectomy is done for any reason.

Result

Table 1: ASA status wise distribution of study participants

ASA Status	Dexmedetomidine	Fentanyl	Total
1	21 70.00%	23 76.70%	44 73.30%
2	9 30.00%	7 23.30%	16 26.70%
Total	30 100.00%	30 100.00%	60 100.00%

Pearson Chi-Square=0.341a P-VALUE= 0.559 (Not significant)

In this study there is no significant association between ASA status and our study groups, p-value is more than 0.05 which is not significant

Table 2: Comparison of baseline vitals in between groups

Baseline	Dexmedetomidine		Fentanyl		p-value
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	
PR	81.67	10.71	86.4	10.6	0.091 (not significant)
SBP	124.67	7.64	126.6	6.71	0.302 (not significant)
DBP	82.07	5.88	82.27	7.79	0.911 (not significant)
MAP	94.5	6.26	94.97	7.88	0.8 (not significant)
SpO ₂	98	0.74	97.93	0.69	0.72 (not significant)
RR	13.47	1.38	13.53	1.36	0.851 (not significant)

In this study there is no significant difference in all the vitals (pulse rate, systolic BP, diastolic BP, MAP, SpO₂, Respiratory rate) before surgery. p-value in all vitals more than 0.05 which is not significant

Table 3: Comparison of post-operative vitals in between groups

	Dexmedetomidine		Fentanyl		p-value
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	
PR	84.2	10.39	88.33	9.07	0.106 (not significant)
SBP	126.2	6.18	126.53	6.5	0.839 (not significant)
DBP	82.13	6.21	82.33	5.07	0.892(not significant)
MAP	95.43	7.34	95	6.57	0.81 (not significant)
SpO2	98.27	0.58	98.4	0.67	0.416(not significant)
RR	13.47	1.17	13.2	1	0.345(not significant)

In this study there is no significant difference in all the vitals (pulse rate, systolic bp, diastolic bp, MAP, SpO₂, Respiratory rate) before surgery. p- value in all vitals more than 0.05 which is not significant

Table 4: Comparison of VAS score in between groups

VAS	Dexmedetomidine		Fentanyl		p-value
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	
30min	19.23	7.63	33.13	5.38	0.00 (significant)
1hr	28.47	8.30	40.87	4.86	0.00 (significant)
4hr	35.53	9.09	48.70	4.85	0.00 (significant)
8hr	44.07	8.24	56.80	4.85	0.00 (significant)
12hr	52.20	8.44	64.50	4.61	0.00 (significant)
16hr	59.97	9.25	71.97	4.31	0.00 (significant)
24 hrs	67.17	9.40	79.87	4.52	0.00 (significant)

In this study there is significant difference between VAS score of both groups during 30 min, 1hour, 4 hour, 8 hour, 12 hour, 16 hour, and 24 hour followup. p- value are less than 0.05 in all followup which is significant.

Table 5: Comparison of NRS score in between groups

NRS	Dexmedetomidine		Fentanyl		p-value
	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	
30min	1.40	0.62	2.53	0.63	0.00 (significant)
1hr	2.00	0.95	3.07	0.58	0.00 (significant)
4hr	2.83	0.95	4.03	0.61	0.00 (significant)
8hr	3.60	0.81	4.97	0.56	0.00 (significant)
12hr	4.40	0.89	5.70	0.60	0.00 (significant)
16hr	5.23	0.86	6.40	0.62	0.00 (significant)
24 hrs	5.97	0.61	7.33	0.71	0.00 (significant)

In this study there is significant difference between NRS score of both groups during 30 min, 1hour, 4 hour, 8 hour, 12 hour, 16 hour, and 24 hour followup. p- value are less than 0.05 in all followup which is significant.

In this study Mean NRS score was significantly higher in fentanyl group then dexmedetomidine group during followup.

Table 6: Comparison of Duration of analgesia and Total analgesia requirement in between groups

	Group	Mean	SD	p- value
	Duration of analgesia	Dexmedetomidine	380.2	
Fentanyl		92.5	31.32	
Total analgesia require-ment	Dexmedetomidine	85.45	33.2	<0.0001
	Fentanyl	179.2	36.52	

In this study mean Duration of analgesia in dexmedetomidine group significantly higher than fentanyl group, p-value is <0.0001 which is less than 0.05 which is highly significant.

In this study total number of analgesia requirement was significantly higher in fentanyl group then dexmedetomidine group, p-value is <0.0001 which is less than 0.05 which is highly significant.

Discussion

In our study the 30 patients given ropivacaine with fentanyl or 30 patients given ropivacaine with dexmedetomidine were comparable with respect to

ASA grading, mean age, gender, and weight. [9] and Hemodynamic parameters like mean heart rate, mean SpO₂, mean SBP, mean DBP, mean MAP and mean RR [10]. A study by Bindra TK et al. 2017 evaluated the Preemptive Analgesic effect of Intraperitoneally Instilled Ropivacaine in patients undergoing Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy. In Two equal groups of 50 patients Group A received 3mg/kg ropivacaine with 100ml of NS before creation of pneumoperitoneum and Group B received 3mg/kg ropivacaine with 100ml of NS after completion of surgery. [11] The ASA grading, mean age, gender, and weight. And heart rate,

SpO₂ mean SBP, mean DBP and MAP of both the groups at all the times was statistically insignificant ($P>0.05$) which is similar to our study. [12]

In our study, Mean VAS score at 30 minute postoperatively was lower among the patients given intraperitoneal ropivacaine with dexmedetomidine as compared to the patients given ropivacaine with fentanyl and was statistically significant. A study done by Chiruvella S et al. noted statistically significant difference with $p<0.05$ between the study groups Ropivacaine and Ropivacaine+ Dexmedetomidine with mean VAS score at different time intervals uptill 24 hours postoperatively. Calculated mean VAS in RD group than in R group was significantly lower (1.86 ± 0.46 vs 4.7 ± 0.94) in 24 hours postoperatively that is in concordance with our present study.[13]

In our study, Mean NRS score at 30 minute postoperatively was lower among the patients given intraperitoneal ropivacaine with dexmedetomidine as compared to the patients given ropivacaine with fentanyl and was statistically significant [11]. A Study conducted by Das DT at el. in 90 patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy this patients were equally separated into 3 groups, Group S administered 35 ml of NS, Group B administered 35 ml of 0.25% of bupivacaine and Group R administered 0.375% ropivacaine intraperitoneally after completion of surgery .pain scores was assessed by using NRS postoperatively upto 24 hours after surgery. Mean duration of analgesia in Group R was double than the duration of analgesia in Group B and 3 times to duration of analgesia than Group S. this difference was statistically significant and in concordance with our present study. [14]

In our study mean total duration of analgesia was significantly higher in (patients administered ropivacaine with dexmedetomidine as compared to ropivacaine with fentanyl (380.2 ± 111.2 vs 92.5 ± 31.32) which was resulted statistically significant. A study conducted by Chiruvella S et al in the patients posted for elective undergoing laparoscopic hysterectomy. The time to demand for first dose of analgesia was longer (126 ± 24 min vs 59 ± 13 min) and total analgesic consumption was also low(95 ± 15 mg vs 175 ± 75 mg) in RD group as compare to R group that showed similar result to our present study. [13]

In our study complications were noted in less than 20% of the patients in both the groups. Nausea, vomiting and pruritis were seen in 4 patients whom intraperitoneal ropivacaine instilled with fentanyl. Shoulder pain was reported in 2 patients of each Group. There was no episode of hypotension, bradycardia, arrhythmia, respiratory depression and other life threatening side effects among both the groups. A similar study by Shukla U et al. noted

there is no significant difference in regard to the adverse effects among the three study groups ($P>0.05$). Only 5 (12.5%) patients in group with bupivacaine and dexmedetomidine suffered from shoulder pain as compared to 16 (40%) in group with bupivacaine and tramadol and 28 (70%) patients in bupivacaine only showed some similarity to our study our study. [15]

Conclusion

There was significant difference in the VAS score and NRS among the patients given ropivacaine with fentanyl and ropivacaine with dexmedetomidine resulted statistically significant ($P<0.05$). That means patients received ropivacaine with dexmedetomidine having better postoperative analgesia with total duration of analgesia was longer . And time for demand of first dose of rescue analgesia was longer and total dose of analgesia requirement is also lower which was resulted statistically significant also ($P<0.05$).

The overall adverse effects observed nausea, vomiting and shoulder pain were less in patients received ropivacaine with dexmedetomidine but comparable in patients given either ropivacaine with fentanyl or ropivacaine with dexmedetomidine, however there was no significant difference in the occurrence of postoperative adverse effects ($P>0.05$).

References

1. Lamont, Leigh A., William J. Tranquilli, and Kurt A. Grimm. "Physiology of pain." *Veterinary Clinics: Small Animal Practice* 30.4(200 0): 703-728.
2. Garimella V, Cellini C. Postoperative pain control. *Clinics in colon and rectal surgery*. 20 13 Sep;26(03):191-6.
3. Gupta A, Kaur K, Sharma S, Goyal S, Arora S, Murthy RS. Clinical aspects of acute post-operative pain management & its assessment. *Journal of advanced pharmaceutical technology & research*. 2010 Apr;1(2):97.
4. Smit-Fun VM, Cox PB, Buhre WF. Role of the anaesthetist in postoperative care. *Journal of British Surgery*. 2020 Jan;107(2):e8-10.
5. Kirkpatrick DR, McEntire DM, Smith TA, Dueck NP, Kerfeld MJ, Hamsch ZJ, Nelson TJ, Reisbig MD, Agrawal DK. Transmission pathways and mediators as the basis for clinical pharmacology of pain. *Expert review of clinical pharmacology*. 2016 Oct 2;9(10):1363-8 7.
6. Ricciotti E, FitzGerald GA. Prostaglandins and inflammation. *Arteriosclerosis, thrombosis, and vascular biology*. 2011 May;31(5):986-10 00.
7. Polychronidis A, Laftsidis P, Bounovas A, Simopoulos C. Twenty years of laparoscopic

- cholecystectomy: Philippe Mouret—March 17, 1987. JSLS: Journal of the Society of Laparoscopic Surgeons. 2008 Jan;12(1):109.
8. Gurusamy K, Junnarkar S, Farouk M, Davidson BR. Meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials on the safety and effectiveness of day-case laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Journal of British Surgery. 2008 Feb;95(2):161-8.
 9. Chiruvella S, Nallam SR. Intraperitoneal instillation of ropivacaine plus dexmedetomidine for pain relief after laparoscopic hysterectomy: A comparison with ropivacaine alone. Journal of Dr. NTR University of Health Sciences. 2016 Apr 1;5(2):93.
 10. Babu R, Jain P, Sherif L. Intraperitoneal instillation: Ropivacaine vs. bupivacaine for post operative pain relief in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Int J Health Sci Res. 2013;3(12):42-7.
 11. Oza VP, Parmar V, Badheka J, Nanavati DS, Taur P, Rajyaguru AM. Comparative study of postoperative analgesic effect of intraperitoneal instillation of dexmedetomidine with bupivacaine and bupivacaine alone after laparoscopic surgery. Journal of Minimal Access Surgery. 2016 Jul;12(3):260.
 12. Bindra TK, Kumar P, Rani P, Kumar A, Bariar H. Preemptive analgesia by intraperitoneal instillation of ropivacaine in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Anesthesia, essays and researches. 2017 Jul;11(3):740.
 13. Chiruvella S, Nallam SR. Intraperitoneal instillation of ropivacaine plus dexmedetomidine for pain relief after laparoscopic hysterectomy: A comparison with ropivacaine alone. Journal of Dr. NTR University of Health Sciences. 2016 Apr 1;5(2):93.
 14. Das NT, Deshpande C. Effects of intraperitoneal local anaesthetics bupivacaine and ropivacaine versus placebo on postoperative pain after laparoscopic cholecystectomy: a randomised double blind study. Journal of clinical and diagnostic research: JCDR. 2017 Jul;11(7): UC 08.
 15. Shukla U, Prabhakar T, Malhotra K, Srivastava D, Malhotra K. Intraperitoneal bupivacaine alone or with dexmedetomidine or tramadol for post-operative analgesia following laparoscopic cholecystectomy: A comparative evaluation. Indian journal of anaesthesia. 2015 Apr; 59(4):234.